

Improving student's virtue character through the perryso dialogue model

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ABSTRACT

The results of needs assessments for a number of universities show that virtuous character behavior shows a number of problems that require efforts by universities to carry out massive and planned virtuous character education movements. The perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification was developed to overcome a number of problems related to the good character of students. This guide product is suitable for use and application to students because it meets the theoretical and practical aspects of acceptance. The product has met the elements of suitability of the guide format, acceptability in terms of psychological material and suitability of the guide content with the criteria of usefulness, accuracy, convenience, attractiveness, and appropriateness. Thus, the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of Universitas Negeri Malang (UM) students is suitable for use by lecturers. Building the virtuous character of (UM) students can provide significant changes to students' thinking processes which include critical, analogical, and association aspects. Product advantages: i) the dialogue guide is scientific, which means this guide is tested empirically through an acceptance test stage by experts and ii) this guide is complete, which means the guide contains material concepts about virtue character along with instruments to determine the success of implementing dialogue activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most serious societal problems amidst the onslaught of disruptive technology which has almost affected every aspect of life, including the spiritual aspect, is the expression of attitudes and behavior, especially among young adults, which no longer reflect the noble character values of the nation and religion [1]–[4]. This character disorientation occurs as a result of society's separation from various religious ideologies and religious structures that have been in force for a long time. Global challenges, social, and cultural changes and future challenges must be fortified and anticipated with quality education and in accordance with national values, cultural values and religious values [5]–[7]. Therefore, it is absolutely necessary to formulate character education that is appropriate to the current situation in facing the changes and challenges of the times and is in line with the needs of students in the future.

The formation of personal character is carried out through a systematic and continuous process. A person's strong character, especially students, has a big influence in creating a good social life. Character building efforts are nothing new in Indonesia, several studies related to character building efforts include

research conducted by Hambali [8] related to Javanese cultural values in the implementation of character education and Maisyarah *et al.* [9] research related to strengthening student character through Pancasila values. As well as research Mulyono *et al.* [10] with the title "Internalization of character education during the covid-19 pandemic through islamic education". Some of these titles represent that efforts to build self-character in students continue to be made. Apart from Indonesia, character issues and character building efforts are also carried out in several other countries, such as in England [11], in the United States [12], in Greece [13], [14], China [15], Philippines, and also in India [11]. Thus, it is clear that character building efforts are a crucial thing to do.

Students, as the next generation of the nation's future, are human resources that need to be developed well and seriously, not only limited to mastering science and technology, but also developing their character and personality. As mandated in Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system, the complete development of Indonesian humans is not enough to just emphasize the physical-intellectual aspect, but must also work on the mental-spiritual side. Remembering that a person's character will color a person's pattern of attitudes, actions, and thought patterns, such as John Dewey, makes moral philosophy the basis for developing educational theories [16]. Dewey's basic concept of moral education is moral consideration in the process of assessment and practice [16], [17]. Without good personal character, humans will not be able to create a social order that upholds a person's dignity. Strengthening character values in students is not enough just with theoretical learning carried out in class. Strengthening these character values needs to be optimized through a habituation process [18], [19].

Universitas Negeri Malang (UM) has actually implemented a character development program through various activities, both academic and non-academic. Through academic channels, character development at UM is carried out by maximizing general compulsory courses, namely: religious education, Pancasila education, citizenship education, and Indonesian language education. Character development through non-academic channels is manifested through seminars, workshops, ceremonies, celebrations of holidays, and the like. In general, character development efforts in the UM environment are carried out in the form of socialization and facilitation, which are aligned with the policies and needs of each unit. Based on the results of the initial assessment (pre-assessment), character development activities at UM leave many things that require improvement and improvement. First, there is no formulation of standard character values that reflect UM's identity as excellence in learning innovation. Second, the description of behavior as a derivative of character values has not been explained in detail so that the explanation is very subjective and has multiple interpretations. Third, approaches and methods for internalizing character values have not been formulated explicitly. As a result, strategies and programs for intervention and habituation of character values at UM have not been properly standardized.

Responding to the problems of character development at UM mentioned above, it is necessary to have an academic text that can be guided by all UM academics. The development of the academic text is based on 5 (five) main values which reflect UM's identity, which are then reduced to 28 sub-values. The formulation of character values is then translated into a description of behavior [20], which is accompanied by internalization strategies and programs (in the form of intervention and habituation). To realize the noble goals above, this character building academic text was developed within the framework of research and development. The urgency of character education at the tertiary level finds momentum when integrity, politeness, discipline, honesty, and nationalism among students are increasingly declining. So this encourages immediate intensification of the development of national character in a sustainable manner. The application of character education within the scope of higher education has a juridical basis in Articles 4 and 5 of Law 12 of 2012, which states that one of the functions and objectives of higher education is to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty and have noble character, be healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, skilled, competent, and cultured for the benefit of the nation.

In line with the juridical basis above, UM as one of the educational and educational personnel institutions which has experienced an expansion of its mandate has a commitment to implementing and overseeing the formation of the character of the Indonesian nation through education and non-education, as well as being a source of enthusiasm and inspiration to develop UM as a higher education institutions that are oriented towards realizing the aspired excellence and providing services to policy makers and the community in the educational and non-educational fields. UM's identity as excellent in learning innovation has become the philosophical and technical foundation in every implementation of learning activities, including character education. The development of character education at UM is based on the universal insight of lifelong learning, education for all and education for sustainable development, which is manifested in UM's vision, mission, and goals. More concretely, UM's goal is to produce graduates who have academic and professional competence, who are devout, have noble character, are intelligent, independent, have national commitment, and are able to develop professionally. This commitment is a heavy duty and responsibility and must be carried out by UM as an institution that produces teaching and educational personnel for all levels of education and non-educational personnel in various fields of life.

Responding to the challenges and needs for formulating character education, UM formulated five main character values, namely honesty, integrity, communicative, intelligent, and visionary. The formulation of character values developed by UM refers to a prophetic approach. Prophetic superior values are believed to be able to change human civilization for the better which includes four character values, namely honesty, integrity, communicativeness, and intelligence. These four character values reflect a person who is always guided by conscience and truth (conscience center), maintains professionalism and commitment (highly committed), masters communication skills (communication skills), while being able to solve problems (problem solver) [21]–[23]. In order to support these four character values, UM students are expected to have visionary character values so that they are able to respond to all the dynamics and challenges of the times, which are closely related to the nature of full innovation that prioritizes the dimension of future insight.

Responding to the challenges and needs for the formulation of character education, researchers developed the Perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification, building the virtuous character of UM students. The first aim of this research is to develop an instrument for measuring virtuous character in higher education and the second is to develop models for fostering virtuous character of students in tertiary institutions. Thus, the development of the Perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification is a step forward in enriching character education in higher education institutions. This model not only focuses on the formation of virtuous character but also provides practical strategies for implementing these values in the daily lives of students, paving the way for the creation of a young generation with high integrity and ready to face future challenges.

2. METHOD

The virtue character development model developed follows the educational software development model in general as stated by several experts [24], [25]; and by paying attention to the development procedure steps (forgiveness). The procedures that will be carried out in developing the virtuous character development model have relatively the same characteristics as Dick *et al.* [25] instructional system development model; namely i) oriented towards activities to produce development products in the form of virtuous character development models, ii) development activities can be carried out both individually and in groups, iii) emphasizes the development or selection of materials, and iv) through repeated trials. Next, the steps for developing a treatment model in general include [26], [27]: i) selecting and determining topics and sources of development material, ii) analyzing the content structure and design format of source content, iii) tracking sources of experience messages, iv) selecting sources. experience sources according to needs, v) adaptation of source message design material and format, vi) determination of design concept, vii) design program, viii) tight tissue design, ix) trial, and x) final work.

The data to be collected includes i) model feasibility which includes, among other things, design, procedures, structure, objectives and content of the virtuous character development model provided by experts, ii) model feasibility data which includes, among other things: suitability, attractiveness with lecturer subjects, and iii) data on the results of trials of awareness data collection instruments. Data on the effectiveness of the virtuous character development model from the results of limited field trials comes from students. In this research, there are three categories of instruments, namely i) treatment instruments as application formats for the virtuous character development model, ii) model validation instruments, and iii) research data collection instruments. The main objective of carrying out validation is to create information that explains the level of feasibility of the virtuous character development model. To what extent can the virtue character development model be applied?

Model feasibility data, which includes design, procedures, structure, objectives, and contents of the model, was obtained from reviewers (multimedia experts and psychology experts), in the form of qualitative data and quantitative data. Qualitative data is responses in the form of suggestions given by reviewers. The analysis carried out was descriptive analysis in the form of analysis of descriptions of responses. These suggestions are selected based on their relevance. Suggestions that are considered relevant are used as material for revising the model tool. Meanwhile, quantitative data is in the form of assessment data obtained from instruments in the form of questionnaires. The analysis carried out for this data was by calculating the percentage of each assessment criterion in each aspect.

Data from lecturers and students regarding the feasibility of the model was analyzed using qualitative and descriptive analysis techniques. Data regarding the trial results of the data collection instruments were analyzed using alpha reliability analysis techniques, while the validity of the instruments was analyzed using factor analysis. Meanwhile, effectiveness trial data were analyzed using different test techniques (t-test).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

Before the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of UM students is used as a guide for developing virtuous character to be applied to students, it is necessary to carry out a theoretical and practical acceptance test. To fulfill the acceptance test, the researcher conducted expert tests related to: i) guide material for the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification, building the virtuous character of UM students, and ii) media guide for the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification, building the virtuous character of UM students and the acceptance of practitioners through expert testing user candidate.

The expert test on the material for developing the virtuous character of UM students was carried out by two experts. The first material expert test has the latest educational qualification of a doctoral degree and has 25 years of teaching experience. The second material expert test has 20 years of teaching experience and his latest education is a Ph.D. These two experts are in developing the virtuous character of UM students from the Indonesian Guidance and Counseling Association and lecturers in developing the virtuous character of UM students from the Malik Ibrahim State Islamic University of Malang.

The media expert test was carried out by two experts. The first media expert test was carried out by a media expert who had 15 years of teaching experience and his most recent education was a Ph.D. Meanwhile, the second media expert test was carried out by a media expert who had 10 years of teaching experience and his latest education was a Ph.D. These two experts are lecturers at the faculty of science and technology, Sunan Ampel State Islamic University, Surabaya. Products are assessed in terms of acceptability aspects, namely usefulness, accuracy, attractiveness, convenience, and appropriateness.

The prospective user test was carried out to obtain data in the form of assessments, suggestions and criticism for improvements and recommendations from prospective product users, namely UM lecturers. This prospective user test is used to assess products based on aspects of acceptability, namely usefulness, accuracy, attractiveness, convenience, and appropriateness. This prospective user test will also produce data in the form of suggestions and recommendations from prospective product users which will be used as a basis for revising the development product produced as the final product of this research and development. The prospective user test was carried out by two lecturers. The assessment data from potential users is in the form of quantitative and qualitative data. All data from the material expert test, media expert test and assessment test for potential users of the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of UM students for users was quantitatively analyzed using the interrater agreement model [28], [29]. The following is a recap of quantitative data from product test results.

Based on the data in Table 1, the test results of the product being developed have met product acceptance which has been validated by material experts, media experts and potential users. The perryso dialogue model guide product based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students has also met product acceptance which has been practically validated by potential users and tested for product effectiveness. Furthermore, qualitative data obtained from material expert tests, media expert tests and potential users is data in the form of suggestions, criticism and input. The following is a summary of the qualitative data.

Table 1. Recap of product test results

Material expert test	Score	Category	Validation classification
Media expert test	1	D	Very high
Test prospective users	0.75	D	Very high
Test potential users	1	D	Very high

In Table 2 you can see the qualitative data obtained from material experts, media experts, and potential users. The qualitative data is in the form of input, suggestions and criticism of the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of UM students. Input provided by material experts, media experts, and potential users will be used to perfect the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students. After being revised, based on the results of qualitative data analysis from material experts, media experts, and potential users, it shows that the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of UM students has fulfilled five aspects of acceptance including usefulness, accuracy, attractiveness, convenience, and appropriateness.

Table 2. Recap of qualitative product test data

Comments, suggestions, and input	Expert	Status
The formulation of the aim of preparing the guideline needs to be operationalized, for example user lecturers can carry out CBM-based perryso dialogue procedures.	Material expert 1	Has been revised
Prepare an example of a verbatim dialogue to be used as a guide for the expert's speech.	Material expert 1	Has been revised
In chapter III, before presenting the perryso dialogue model procedure based on cognitive behavior modification and the initial to final stages, it is best to provide an explanation regarding examples of sentences spoken.	Material expert 2	Has been revised
In the description of the stages of the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification, from beginning to end, it is best to include an example of an audio-visual model so that lecturers as users get clarity or examples of the implementation of this counseling, especially in the core part of.	Material expert 2	Has been revised
The title on the cover should be in capital letters media expert 1	Media expert 1	Has been revised
The word "by" can be replaced by "developer".	Media expert 1	Has been revised
The word "model" (in the main part) or (in other parts) should be supplemented with the words "audio visual model".	Media expert 1	Has been revised
Several images relevant to the model may be included to add to the communicativeness of the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification.	Media expert 2	Has been revised
If there were pictures as illustrative examples, it would be even better.	Media expert 1	Has been revised
User lecturers need examples of sentences to be delivered for each stage in the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students.	Prospective user 1	Has been revised
guide to the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of um students is good and can be applied in schools.	Prospective user1	Has been revised

3.2. Discussion

Research and development of the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students for junior high school students produced the product of the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students. The content of the material in this guide is based on the concept of cognitive behavior modification expressed by Meichenbaum in the perryso dialogue model [30]–[32]. The product developed has met validated product acceptance by material experts, media experts, and potential users.

The perryso dialogue model guide product based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students has also met product acceptance which has been practically validated by potential users and tested for product effectiveness. The perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students has met product acceptance based on the assessment of media experts. The results of the learning media expert assessment stated that the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of UM students was appropriate with an expert validity of 0.75. The validity index from learning media experts for this development product is included in the high category. This assessment from learning media experts shows that this development product is suitable for use by lecturers in terms of product format.

The assessment of learning media experts is based on product suitability criteria which state that good criteria in developing educational products include having to fulfill usability, suitability, appropriateness and accuracy. In the development of the perryso dialogue model guide product based on cognitive behavior modification, building the virtuous character of UM students, it adapted the product's feasibility criteria with several developments that were adapted to the conditions and needs of product users. The criteria for learning media experts are usefulness, accuracy, convenience, attractiveness, and appropriateness [33], which are in accordance with the established criteria.

The perryso dialogue model guide product based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students has sufficient descriptions to make it easier for user lecturers to understand the main part, accompanied by an explanation of the use of the audio-visual model at the link. The perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students was also assessed by two psychology experts and two potential users. Psychological experts provide an acceptance assessment of the content of the material and procedures in this guide. The results of the psychological material expert's assessment stated that the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for fostering the virtuous character of UM students had high product acceptability with an expert validity index of 1. The psychological material expert's assessment showed that the product was suitable in terms of content for user use. Practically, product acceptability is demonstrated through the assessment of potential product users, namely lecturers. The lecturer provides an assessment of the content of the material and procedures for implementing the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of UM students. The assessment of psychology teachers in

schools shows a practically acceptable category with expert validity index 1. Perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students is considered suitable to be used as a guide for lecturers in developing the virtuous character of UM students.

Effective character education plays a crucial role in developing holistic and responsible individuals [34]–[36]. Beyond just supporting academic success, a comprehensive and interactive model in character building emphasizes honing ethical values, promoting empathy, and strengthening integrity [37], [38]. In an education era marked by complexity and diversity, this strategy is key in preparing students for various real-world challenges. Through character education, students are encouraged not only to pursue intellectual excellence but also to build a strong moral foundation, enabling them to act with wisdom and moral courage in every situation [39]. The implications of this research indicate that the development of character education models is crucial not only for university students but also requires further adaptation and development for school students [40], [41]. This suggests the need for inclusive and flexible strategies that can be implemented at different levels of education [42]. By extending the scope of this model, character education can become more integrated into the curriculum of primary and secondary education, thus preparing students with a strong character foundation from an early age [43].

The perryso dialogue model guide product based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students has high expert relevance value from the first and second potential users. Acceptance of a product that is in the high category based on assessments from potential users indicates that the product is ready for use. The assessment of potential users of this product is the basis for wider publication of the product development for all lecturers. The limitations in this study include a lack of discussion on the long-term impact assessment of the model's implementation on student character development. Therefore, subsequent research that tracks the student process post-model implementation can provide more conclusive data regarding the model's success.

4. CONCLUSION

The acceptance of the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification for developing the virtuous character of UM students is based on the results of previous research which also produced products. The acceptability of the material content in this guide is based on the concept of cognitive behavior modification expressed by Meichenbaum where in the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification for building the virtuous character of UM students, students make analogies to be able to evaluate the objects they observe and learn in various situations. This condition will allow psychology teachers to explore various forms of statements as stimuli for higher level thinking that are expected to emerge. In this research, the behavior to be improved is Hots thinking skills. The perryso dialogue model is based on cognitive behavior modification, building the virtuous character of UM students which focuses on changing cognitive and behavioral skills combined with techniques that can reveal the critical side so that the dialogue process becomes more comfortable.

The technique used in the perryso dialogue model guide based on cognitive behavior modification to develop the virtuous character of UM students is dialogue action. Through dialogue, it is hoped that it can stimulate individual cognitive processes and reveal a critical attitude towards objects which provides opportunities to increase insight, self-reflection, and individual perspectives on objects and focus of thinking. The suitability of this concept is the basis for the acceptance of the content of the dialogue material, namely the perryso dialogue model based on cognitive behavior modification, building the virtuous character of UM students.

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